

Observation Report of the Partial Solar Eclipse in Majadahonda

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Abstract

This report details the observations made during the partial solar eclipse on March 29, 2025, in Majadahonda, Spain. It includes the observed and predicted contact times, the sources used for the predictions, and a comparison of the obtained data. Additionally, the software developed for eclipse simulation and calculation is described.

1 Introduction

On March 29, 2025, a partial solar eclipse was visible from various regions of Spain, including Majadahonda. This astronomical phenomenon occurs when the Moon partially blocks the Sun from the Earth's perspective. Observing and analyzing solar eclipses is of great interest to both the scientific community and amateur astronomers.

2 Eclipse Predictions

Several sources provided predictions for the eclipse contact times for the Majadahonda location. The following table presents these times:

Source	C1	Maximum	C4
Xavier Jubier [1]	09:48:30 UT	10:40:07 UT	11:33:45 UT
Fred Espenak [2]	09:48:26.4 UT	10:40:03.8 UT	11:33:42.1 UT
Eclipses 2.0 (UB) [3]	09:48:29 UT	10:40:06 UT	11:33:43 UT
pyeclipsesimulator [4]	09:49:01.0 UT	10:40:20.0 UT	11:33:47.5 UT
Stellarium [8]	09:48:32 UT	—	11:33:44 UT
Obs	09:48:27.268 UT	—	11:33:32.013 UT

Table 1: Eclipse contact times according to different sources and actual observations.

3 Eclipse Simulation and Calculation Software

To complement the predictions and perform detailed simulations, a Python-based software named `pyeclipsesimulator` was developed. This program calculates and visualizes solar eclipse-related events. Its main features include:

- Calculation of key solar eclipse events (contacts, magnitude, duration, etc.).
- Location selection via:
 - Municipality or location name (geocoding),
 - Manual coordinates,
 - List of provincial capitals in Spain.
- Automatic altitude retrieval using the Open-Meteo API.
- Manual or automatic star catalog download from Vizier.
- Animated eclipse simulation with and without atmospheric refraction.
- Optional real-horizon data loading.
- Artificial horizon generation via PeakFinder.

The software is available on Zenodo [4].

4 Observations

The partial solar eclipse observations were conducted in Majadahonda using high-precision astronomical equipment. A Schmidt-Cassegrain Celestron 8 telescope was used along with a Sony a7s II camera connected to an AverMedia video capture device. Image acquisition was handled by *SharpCap* software, version 4.1.

Precise time synchronization was critical. It was achieved using *BKT-TIME-SYNC* software version 1.14.0 (by IZ2BKT) connected to the public NTP server `1.es.pool.ntp.org`. Time consistency was verified by comparing the capture system timestamps with a simultaneous mobile phone recording synchronized using the NTP protocol.

During the analysis of the captured frames, the first and fourth contacts were clearly identified:

- **First Contact (C1):** Visually estimated on a full-screen image. The timestamp corresponds to when the lunar limb began to obscure the solar disk: **09:48:27.268 UT**.
- **Fourth Contact (C4):** Automatically determined using a Python algorithm. The algorithm detects the solar limb and records the first frame where a convex contour is identified, marking the end of the eclipse: **11:33:32.013 UT**.

The code used for the automated fourth contact detection is included in the appendix.

5 Data Comparison

A comparison between the observed and predicted times shows a high degree of agreement. The maximum differences are:

- **First Contact (C1):** Max difference: 2.7 seconds.
- **Maximum Eclipse:** Max difference: 4.0 seconds.
- **Fourth Contact (C4):** Max difference: 13.2 seconds.

6 Conclusions

The partial solar eclipse observation in Majadahonda on March 29, 2025, was successful. The data collected closely matches the predictions from various sources, confirming the reliability of modern eclipse prediction tools. Additionally, the development and use of the `pyeclipsesimulator` software proved to be a valuable asset for detailed analysis and planning.

7 Observation Images

Below are selected frames extracted from the recorded video during the eclipse:

Figure 1: Frame corresponding to the first contact (C1): 09:48:27.268 UT

8 Outreach and Live Streaming

As part of the public outreach effort, the eclipse was streamed live on YouTube, allowing viewers to follow the event in real-time from different locations. The stream included live commentary on the phenomenon, the equipment, and astronomical context.

The recording is available at:

<https://www.youtube.com/live/P8v1EVR12Zg?si=3a0ioBG24ndTUN4v>

As of March 30, 2025, the video had received over **1130 views**, contributing to the public dissemination of astronomy.

Figure 2: Frame near the fourth contact (C4): 11:33:32.013 UT

9 Additional Outreach Resources

To further explore and better understand solar eclipses, the Eclipseo blog [7] is recommended. This platform features a wide variety of educational articles and practical guides, including:

- **Shadow Bands:** An intriguing optical phenomenon associated with total solar eclipses.
- **History of Solar Eclipses in Chinese Astronomy:** Insights into the role of eclipses in science, rituals, and politics in ancient China.
- **Educational Resources:** Teaching materials, books, and historical curiosities.
- **Solar Filter Safety Standards:** Information on the ISO 12312-2:2015 standard for safe eclipse viewing.
- **Eclipse Observation Expeditions:** Reports and details from Spanish expeditions dedicated to eclipse observation and outreach.

These resources are useful for both astronomy enthusiasts and professionals preparing for future eclipses.

Figure 3: Equipment setup during the observation

References

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